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Ferron as a Spectrophotometric Reagent for Determination of Vanadium(v)

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A large number of spectrophotometric reagents have been reported for the determination of vanadium. Among these, oxine and its derivatives¹⁻⁵ are widely used for the estimation of the element with or without the use of liquid-liquid extraction. Oxinate systems are not very sensitive and thus the sensitivity as well as the selectivity is improved by the substitution of halide, methyl or sulphonic groups at the appropriate positions of 8-hydroxyquinoline. Ferron (7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid) is found to be the most suitable reagent among the oxine derivatives for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium.

Ferron forms a complex with vanadium(v) extractable into n-butanol⁶. But the recovery of vanadium is not quantitative due to greater solubility of n-butanol in the aqueous phase. Moreover, some of the important elements, tungsten and zirconium interfere seriously in this method and the fate of many elements is not known. The problem of quantitative recovery is overcome by a suitable choice of the solvent having minimum solubility in water. It was reported earlier⁷ that tribenzylamine solution in chloroform could be used for the extraction of vanadium(v)-ferron complex which gives an olive-green extract in the solvent phase.

Accordingly, we present here a more sensitive and selective method for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium after extracting the vanadium(v)-ferron complex into tribenzylamine-chloroform solution.

Experimental

A Perkin-Elmer 550S spectrophotometer equipped with 1 cm matched quartz and silica cells was employed for recording absorption measurements.

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Vanadium(v) stock solution (10 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared from sodium metavanadate, standardised titrimetrically⁸, and diluted to 100 and 10 µg ml⁻¹. Stock solutions of other elements (1-10 mg ml⁻¹) were prepared by dissolving suitable salts in water, or dilute hydrochloric acid. A 1% (w/v) solution of tribenzylamine (TBA) in chloroform was prepared. A 0.15% (w/v) solution of ferron in distilled water was used. Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing solutions of the elements to give the required composition.

Procedure: An aliquot containing $\leq 200\ \mu\text{g}$ o-vanadium(v) was transferred into a 150 ml separatory funnel. Ferron solution (10 ml) and 2 N sulphuric acid (1 ml) were added to it followed by enough distilled water to make the aqueous phase volume to 20 ml. The complex was extracted with tribenzylamine solution (10 ml) in chloroform for 1 min. The two layers were allowed to separate and the solvent phase was drawn into a 25 ml volumetric flask. The extraction was repeated again with TBA-chloroform solution (10 ml). The two extracts were combined and volume was made up to the mark with chloroform. The absorbance of the coloured complex was measured at 390 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Vanadium(v) forms a complex with ferron which is not extracted by benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, methyl isobutyl ketone, isoamyl acetate or ethyl acetate. The complex is extractable with n-butanol⁶ but not recovered 100% even after two extractions. This complex can be extracted quantitatively into TBA-chloroform solution. The absorption spectrum of the olive-green complex of vanadium(v) with ferron in TBA-chloroform solution has been studied. The complex shows a absorption maximum at 390 nm and a small hump in 620-630 nm region. The reagent blank absorbs very strongly at 340 nm which drops sharply to a low value at 370 nm, and beyond it becomes negligibly small. As the complex shows a λ_{max} at 390 nm it is chosen for absorbance measurements.

Effect of variables: The effect of different parameters on the extraction of vanadium(v)-ferron complex is studied. In the study of these variables, 20 ml of aqueous phase containing 5 µg V ml⁻¹ was extracted with equal volume of TBA-chloroform solution and absorbances were measured at 390 nm. On the basis of these studies, the optimum conditions for maximum absorbance are 0.08-0.12 N sulphuric acid, 10-15 ml of 0.1% ferron, 1-2% TBA-chloroform solution and 1-4 min equilibration time.

Beer's law, stability and sensitivity: The olive-green coloured complex of vanadium(v) follows Beer's law up to 10 µg V ml⁻¹ with a Sandell sensitivity of 0.006 µg V cm⁻². The complex is stable for 24 h. Single extraction with 10 ml of 1% TBA-chloroform solutions removes more than 99% of

vanadium but for quantitative recovery second extraction with another 10 ml of extractant is recommended.

Stoichiometry of the complex: The molar composition of the vanadium(V)-ferron complex was studied by Job's method of continuous variations⁹. On the basis of these studies, the composition of the complex extracted into TBA-chloroform solution was found to be 1 : 3 : 2 (metal : ferron : tribenzylamine).

Effect of diverse ions: 1 g each of sodium chloride, sodium sulphate and sodium nitrate was found to have no effect on the extraction of vanadium, 0.5 g of tartaric acid and 0.1 g of acetate and phosphate do not interfere. Fluoride and citrate can be tolerated only upto 50 mg. Oxalate, ascorbic acid and EDTA interfere seriously.

Tungsten(VI) interferes by forming a cream colour emulsion on shaking with TBA-chloroform solution which can be prevented by the addition of 0.5 g tartaric acid to the solution before adding ferron. Barium, strontium and lead give insoluble sulphates without affecting the extraction of the complex. Thorium hydrolyses and causes emulsion formation, the emulsion being broken by addition of ethanol. Silicic acid formed from silicates remains in the aqueous phase and causes no interference. Chromium(VI) interferes by forming orange colour extract but chromium(III) is not extracted under the optimum conditions. Bismuth(III) gets hydrolysed, thus limiting its tolerance to 5 mg. The interference of antimony(III) can be overcome by the addition of 0.5 g tartaric acid. Titanium and zirconium give yellow coloured extract on shaking with TBA-chloroform solution but both the elements can be tolerated upto 5 mg if 50 mg of fluoride is added before ferron addition. Under these conditions, the tolerance limits for various elements in 20 ml of solution are : 50 mg

each of W, Co, Ni, Mn, Pb, Al, Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba, Be, Hg, Si, Zn, Ag, Tl, Cd, Th and La ; 5 mg each of U, Bi and Sb. Fe, Mo and Cu interfere seriously.

Applications: The wide applicability of the method was tested by the satisfactory analysis of a variety of synthetic samples containing vanadium up to 200 µg in the aliquot. The method is quite selective for vanadium determination in the presence of large amounts of Ni, Co, Mn, W, Zn, Al, U, Pb, Cd, Th, Ti and Zr. The proposed method is quite simple and rapid as it takes less than 10 min for vanadium determination after the preparation of vanadium solution. It is one of the sensitive methods available for vanadium determination and could be used in the analysis of natural samples and industrial products.

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